

Automated BIM QA/QC procedures with practical application

JULIO JOAQUIN SALABERRI MARTIN

Supervisors:

Tomo Cerovšek

Faculty of Civil and Geodetic Engineering, University of Ljubljana, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Andraž Starc

IBE d.d., Ljubljana, Slovenia Franc Sinur

IBE d.d., Ljubljana, Slovenia

Abstract

The increase of adoption of BIM methodology in construction projects, and the increase of BIM maturity in organizations and project teams, has led to an increase of the amount and diversity of requirements that the information in the BIM models need to satisfy, from building regulations, through the construction process, all the way to the built asset management.

Design companies need to take into account these requirements for the development of their design, and they are responsible of producing their design and information in compliance with those requirements. For this, design companies should have proper Quality Assurance and Quality Control plans and processes that ensure the quality of the information produced. Model checking is a necessary activity as part of the QA/QC plans to ensure that compliance between the information and requirements. However, still in many design companies this model checking is carried out by manual or semi-automated procedures that need a tangible amount of time and therefore, human resources.

This thesis aims to define a generic workflow to implement automated rule-based checks that allow to validate the alphanumeric information content of the developed BIM models in the design stages of a project life cycle in the environment of the BIM Authoring Tool, from the perspective of a design company, based on the information available in the literature. The workflow can be carried out in an isolated manner or can be integrated into the design phase processes of such design company. Afterwards, the applicability of the workflow has

been tested in a case study, making use of tools that are available on the market and allow to perform automated checks on the alphanumerical information of the model and evaluate the compliance of this information with alphanumerical requirements.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/1PN5Xv6VYBA>

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